

Mychal Matsemela Odom and Daniel Bankole Widener

Title: From South Africa to South Central L.A.: Transnational Black Protest, Celebrity, and the Cultural Boycott

ABSTRACT

Using Los Angeles as a case study, this essay explores transnational Black protest, celebrity, and the cultural boycott. Although cultural activism was a staple of anti-apartheid activity across the world, Los Angeles was distinguished in the U.S. context by an ongoing campaign that mobilised African Americans for the purpose of confronting Black celebrities who violated the cultural boycott. Organising around the cultural boycott took place alongside novel forms of Black American celebrity whose epicentre was Los Angeles, and amidst worsening social conditions for ordinary Black Americans. In seeking to constrain the activities of Black celebrities even as they critiqued the increasing depoliticisation of African American life, Black radicals injected class politics into an anti-racist struggle while leveraging the cultural capital of Black Americans. As part of a broader effort to highlight the commonalities between social conditions in South Africa and Southern California, work around the cultural boycott invigorated a Black American critique of American social conditions while also demonstrating the value of cultural work as a strategic terrain for transnational political activity.

KEYWORDS: Apartheid, cultural politics, California, black radicalism

On June 29, 1990, Nelson Mandela addressed a 70,000-person crowd at the Los Angeles Coliseum. Coming four months after his release from Robben Island, Mandela's swing through Southern California marked the penultimate stop in a whirlwind tour that took him to eight American cities in the course of 12 days. In Los Angeles, Mandela spoke at events at which movie stars, athletes, and entertainers were highly visible. In addition to the public event at the Coliseum, private events were held with "stars and starmakers" like Peter Weller, Jane Fonda, Richard Dreyfuss, Diana Ross, Sidney Poitier, Harry Belafonte, and Danny Glover. At one fundraiser organised by the Hollywood Women's Political Committee and Artists United Against Apartheid, the crowd of A-listers could see that Mandela had made a quick adjustment to Los Angeles. Expected at 5 p.m., Mandela's convoy arrived at the dinner at 9:30 p.m., before joining the Coliseum audience at 11 p.m. (Hall 1990).

The "stars and starmakers" offered effusive praise. Gregory Peck introduced Mandela as "the man who awakened the conscience of America," while Los Angeles Mayor Tom Bradley compared the South African to the Rev. Martin Luther King, Jr. At the Coliseum,

Quincy Jones and Lionel Richie took the stage with Hugh Masekela and Bill Cosby, then at the height of his popularity. Conscious of his audience, Mandela thanked the entertainment world for its support for South Africa's cultural exiles, and made specific mention of creative personalities in attendance who had made direct contributions to the struggle, including Poitier and Belafonte. Urging the maintaining of sanctions "including the cultural boycott," Mandela also offered a gentle rebuke of Hollywood's negative depictions of Africans over many years before speaking of the "city of glamour and splendor...which daily nourished the dreams of millions of people the world over" (Wilkinson and Ford 1990).

American media readily celebrated Mandela's visit. The *New York Times* spoke of "a popular hero hailed by millions who a few months ago were probably giving scant attention to apartheid (Kiffner 1990) while the *Los Angeles Times* described the "unusually" integrated crowds that came to greet him "in this sprawling and segregated city" (Hall 1990). Mandela's visit to the United States came at the apex of one phase of his external symbolic construction via a number of indexical external mass media representations (1987-1990) (Tomaselli and Shepperson 2009). Cast as a preeminent symbol—a totalizing icon of struggle akin to Martin Luther King, Jr. or Gandhi—Mandela's image was being recast away from its radical—especially socialist—associations. As part of this process, Mandela's national trip hewed toward the clichéd. In Washington, Madiba met politicians. In New York City, he traveled to Harlem, the unofficial "capital" of Black America. In Detroit, he was greeted by trade unionists. In Atlanta, he praised Martin Luther King, Jr. While in L.A., he met entertainers and other celebrities.

Amidst the triumphalism that accompanied Mandela's tour, a network of local organizations offered a warning that the celebrations actually marked a setback for solidarity activists. In the run-up to Mandela's visit, the Friends of the ANC and the Frontline States (FANC) released "Lessons for the Anti-Apartheid Movement: Notes from Los Angeles." The document decried the sidelining of longtime groups with strong links to LA's black community, noting that efforts to link conditions in Southern Africa

and South Los Angeles, as well as attempts to keep the pressure on the apartheid state, were at risk of being “shattered” by the opportunism of elite politicians desperate to secure photo-ops. “Mandela will come and go,” the authors noted, “but our goal is to plan for the future...to the ongoing struggle.” Local activists who had on other occasions brought Alfred Nzo, Oliver Tambo, and Chris Hani to L.A. found themselves cast aside by local elected officials. Maxine Waters, who had authored California state legislation mandating the divestment of \$8 billion worth of South African investments held by California public pension funds, came in for particular criticism on the part of Black American leftists who pondered whether “ANC leadership is fully aware of local class issues,” including the presence of African Americans willing to “play into the hands of the (predominantly white) class and power structure.” Waters, they noted, had “a proven history of not respecting...anti-apartheid organizations locally” (Lessons for the Anti-apartheid Movement 1990; Horne 2019, 796).

This “micro-history” of anti-apartheid activity in Los Angeles explores three core themes, namely the development of localized transnational black protest, celebrity, and the cultural boycott. We argue that efforts by a coalition of Black left activists in Los Angeles to impede what they termed “cultural collaboration” with apartheid grew out of a broader framework that drew analogies between South Africa and inner city Los Angeles, and that the turn toward cultural work revealed strategic possibilities leveraged by local activists. Although cultural activism was a staple of anti-apartheid activity across the world, Los Angeles was distinguished in the U.S. context by an ongoing campaign that mobilized African Americans to challenge celebrities who violated injunctions against performing in South Africa. Confrontations with prominent entertainers took place at a critical juncture. Amidst rising resistance inside South Africa, African Americans took notice of the sharp contradiction between worsening social conditions for working-class black Californians and the emergence of new forms of celebrity predicated upon the representation of African Americans as depoliticized symbols of wealth and success. The result was the sharpening of class and anti-imperialist politics within a nominally antiracist campaign. The linkage between conditions in South Africa and Southern California thus invigorated a Black American critique of American social conditions

while also highlighting the efficacy of the cultural realm as a strategic terrain for transnational political activity.

From South Africa to South Central: Anti-apartheid and Black Liberation

The production of a popular critique of Mandela's visit to Southern California offers a reminder that telling the history of the global anti-apartheid movement requires attention not simply to transnational links, but also to popular histories from below. The worldwide struggle against white supremacy in South Africa constituted a unique historical event, arguably the most successful global social movement in history and the final defeat for legalised forms of racial hierarchy and colonialism that had been five centuries in the making. As a complex story that unfolded across boardrooms and battlefields, universities, parliaments, and, most critically, inside South Africa itself, we are in full agreement with the analysis of Hakan Thorn, who argues "that an adequate analysis of the anti-apartheid movement has to pay attention to the construction of networks, organizations, identities, action forms and information flows that transcended borders." (2006, 4)

Expanding bibliography has examined the myriad links between Black North Americans and Southern Africa. Robert Massie's extensive *Loosing the Bonds* touches on black America activism at numerous points (1997). Robert Trent Vinson (2012) and Penny Von Eschen (1997) highlight how the early presence of bodies like the Universal Negro Improvement Association (U.N.I.A.) and the Council on African Affairs ensured that Africans and African Americans were engaging each other's political struggles during the decades in which the full mechanism of legal separation was associated not with South Africa, but with the American South. James Meriwether (2002) sets African American engagement with South Africa alongside attempts to draw connections to struggles in Ethiopia, Ghana, and Kenya. Njubi Nesbitt (2004) calls attention to the various tendencies—leftist, liberal, and nationalist—within the Black American movement in support of Southern African struggles. Brenda Gayle Plummer (2012), Nicholas Grant (2017), and Fanon Che Wilkins (2001) have brought these links through

the turbulent postwar years and through the eventual demise of apartheid. It is important to acknowledge that the frontline states have been included in this literature as well, with substantial studies charting the black North American engagement with political developments in Zimbabwe, Angola, Tanzania, and Mozambique, in particular.

Tales of transnational linkages are generally told as national stories. As a result, it is rare that in-depth approaches highlight local circumstances, contributions, or challenges. Yet to the extent that one core contribution of the “new black power” scholarship has been to highlight the variation in political conditions and organisational methods across the United States, it is worth considering what specific elements relating to the anti-apartheid struggle can be illuminated by a subnational frame (Franklin, 2007, 463-466). During the “long 1960s,” local conditions facilitated specific tactical choices on the part of Black American revolutionaries. In California, for example, firearms laws and militarized policing shaped the emergence of openly armed activism. In New York, decades of Afrocentric activity meant that the distinction between revolutionary and cultural nationalism—which exploded into deadly violence in Southern California—was a lesser concern for radicals who linked Marxist political economy with African names, West African clothing, Swahili greetings, and other “cultural” appropriations.

In the case of the American anti-apartheid movement, similar points can be made. In the 1970s, African Liberation Day rallies in New York City and Boston produced the largest crowds since the heyday of the U.N.I.A. (Nesbitt 2004, 79). A decade later, in Detroit, the San Francisco Bay Area, and upstate New York, radicalized workers were at the forefront of confronting American complicity with the South African system. (Labor Against Apartheid Newsletter, 1984). New York was a site of organizing around diplomatic issues to exclude Pretoria on the world stage, among other issues (Gerald Horne, conversation with the author, 27 October 2019). Washington D.C., of course, was ground zero in the push for sanctions. Activity took place on colleges throughout the United States, although here again the Bay Area’s Berkeley campus stood out for the size and militancy of its student activism (LA Kauffman 2017, 61-74). Across the U.S., a central point should be made: in the context of the reactionary rise of Ronald Reagan, the

intensification of struggles in Southern Africa, especially after 1985, provided a dramatic opportunity for growth on the part of black American left (Boyd 1987).

Despite its strategic location as a site of banking, defense manufacturing, and entertainment, all key sectors of external anti-apartheid activity, the history of popular activism related to South Africa in Southern California is not particularly well known. Between 1975 and 1990, community-based anti-apartheid activities found their primary organizational expression in four groups: the Southern African Support Committee, the Southern Africa Research Project, Unity in Action, and the Friends of the ANC and the Frontline States. The membership of these groups overlapped—Friends of the ANC emerged from an expansion of SASC, of which Unity in Action was a member, while the SARP was a collective whose primary responsibility lay in generating information about Southern African struggles that could be used by L.A.-based activists. These groups were themselves coalitional formations that included both local bodies, like the Los Angeles Student Coalition (of which one of the authors was a member), as well as branch organizations of national groups like the National Anti-Imperialist Movement in Solidarity with African Liberation. Ultimately, Friends of the ANC included representatives from at least eighteen groups.¹

SASC conducted extensive research on conditions throughout Southern Africa, organised drives for material assistance, contributed to consular protests and hosted visits of exiled African activists. In Los Angeles, organisers affiliated with SASC made multiple efforts to link the South African and Black American struggles. For example, SASC sought to build support for a statewide boycott of Bank of America, then America's largest bank,

¹ Member organizations of FANC included the American Friends Service Committee, California Democratic Council, Council of Black Trade Unions, Committee for Health in Southern Africa, Los Angeles 435 Observer Committee to Namibia, Los Angeles Student Coalition (of which author Widener was a member), Mozambique Support Network, NAIMSAL, Patrice Lumumba Coalition, Presbyterian Synod Task Force on Southern Africa, South African International Student Congress, Southern Africa Resource Center, Southern Africa Resource Project (of which Michael Widener, the father of author Widener, was a member), Southern Africa Support Committee, SWAPO Support Committee, Unity in Action, and U.S.-Angola Friendship Society. **I think the paper can do without this footnote – for style and length requirements. AGREED KEYAN**

which held tens of millions of dollars in South African debt.² Noting that the bank had 14 branches in the largely black West Adams district, but had written only ten mortgages that year, SASC contrasted the practice of “redlining” with the extension of credit to a regime confronting a worsening economic situation. The organisation also organised a boycott of Del Monte, noting that the multinational supported illegal fishing in Namibian waters that contributed to African malnutrition, American unemployment, and the violation of various international prohibitions related to Pretoria’s illegal occupation of Namibia. As part of the Del Monte campaign, SASC distributed an extraordinary flowchart explaining agribusiness—from oil wells and mining to restaurants and stores (“Dear Friends” 1976).

² In 1976 alone, Richard Knight (1976) describes the issuance of loans to South Africa from a consortium of 10 US banks totaling \$776M. These loans were critical. Dubow notes the uneven performance of the South African economy during this time. See Dubow, *Apartheid*, 2014, 177-179. Consider deleting this footnote.

(Courtesy of Ron Wilkins)

The Southern Africa Support Coalition took up the issue of sports as well. In 1977, SASC joined an ad hoc group of Los Angeles and Orange County groups protesting against South Africa's participation in the Davis Cup, which took place in the affluent Orange County suburb of Newport Beach. These demonstrations included the physical disruption of matches, and resulted in four unarmed demonstrators being attacked by U.S. tennis champion Tony Trabert, who assaulted protesters with his racket on consecutive days. The organization also participated in efforts to refashion the 1984 Olympiad—still one of the most profitable in history—into an event that would be of some lasting benefit to the predominantly black area in which the core events of swimming and track and field were held. Amidst increased police patrols intended to demonstrate the safety of "inner city" L.A. neighborhoods, and amidst the controversial inclusion of South African-born runner Zola Budd as part of the British Olympic team, community groups organized protests

which attracted up to 10,000 Los Angeles residents drawn by local and international themes (“From Orange State” 1977).

A decade later, the same core group organized an event entitled “From South Africa to South Central Los Angeles: the decline of health care.” Held at the Black Employees Association headquarters, and featuring talks by African American doctor Jan King and Natal-born ANC member Dr. Barry Kistnasamy, panels at the event took up themes such as effect of violence on mental health, racism and reduced access to health care, occupational health in South Africa and the United States, and alternative healing practices. (Committee on Health, 1991). On another occasion, SASC and SARP organized a joint fundraising campaign whose benefits were split equally between the King-Drew Medical Center, a hospital located in an impoverished Black neighborhood (Watts) and Sally Mugabe’s Zimbabwean Child Survival Movement. Friends of the ANC also published an essay, accompanied by multiple workshops, on the “apartheid roots of ‘Black on Black’ violence.” Aimed at local gang members trying to forge peace treaties, these forums drew a direct connection between the deindustrialization of Los Angeles, the suppression of the Black Liberation Movement, and the rise of the crips and bloods while noting the parallels present in South Africa, where the Inkatha/ANC conflict was described as part of a “complex social and economic” situation that could not be explained by the American media because doing so would necessitate “a closer examination of what happens in America’s ghettos” (FANC 1991-1992).

Most crucially, SASC and the FANC cast state violence as the core link between South Central and South Africa. In this they were hardly alone—these analogies were central to black American anti-apartheid activity as a whole. However, the particularly poisonous conditions of local policing gave the issue a specific dynamism. Long before the televised beating of Rodney King, Los Angeles police were considered among the worst in the United States (Felker-Kantor 2018). In the aftermath of the 1965 Watts riots, then Police Chief William Parker had referred to Black Angelenos as “monkeys in a zoo” (Horne 1997, 137.) Over half of all Black Panthers killed in the United States belonged to Los Angeles branches, and the first Special Weapons and Tactics team in the nation was

developed for explicit deployment against black radicals. By the 1980s, Los Angeles Police Chief Daryl Gates had made national news—deploying Vietnam analogies in describing Black youth, offering to lend the SWAT team to the American military, and unleashing his militarized cops indiscriminately upon African Americans. Mike Davis describes one “orgy of violence” in which police destroyed an apartment building before forcing terrified residents to whistle the theme song from a 1960s-era television show (that features a white policeman as a protagonist) while they ran “a gauntlet of police beating them with fists and long steel flashlights ” (Davis 1990, 276).

Whatever the limits of comparison, it is critical to recall that African Americans who drew links between racism and poverty in South Los Angeles and Southern Africa did so against a backdrop in which the head of the Los Angeles Police Department claimed that more blacks died in police chokeholds because “their veins did not open as quickly as *normal people*” (Davis 1975, 22); where mass sweeps dragged thousands of young black men—including the authors of this essay—off the streets every weekend; and where military technologies like dum-dum rounds and automatic rifles were entering everyday police service for the first time in the U.S. (O’Shaughnessy 1988). In the context of inner city neighborhoods that were 80-90% black, the notion of a black majority under siege by a white minority was more than comprehensible. It was obvious, even without the most extreme overtones. In 1989, Black LAPD officers reported white officers wearing swastika rings while on duty and informed their superiors that two white homicide detectives had placed a South Africa flag emblem on their vehicle as they patrolled predominantly Black areas of South Los Angeles (Ford 1989).

As the remainder of this essay shows, Los Angeles activism around the cultural boycott was likewise framed as a transnational struggle that addressed both South African and African American concerns. Black radicals sought to constrain the activities of Black celebrities even as they critiqued the increasing depoliticization of African American life. This political stance injected class politics into an anti-racist struggle while leveraging the cultural capital of Black Americans. It took the form of a kind of “popular front” around cultural activism that could engage the energies of multiple strands of the black left.

Frances E. Williams, for example, who founded a local iteration of Artists Against Apartheid, had for many decades belonged to organisations linked to the Communist Party, including the National Anti-imperialist Movement in Support of African Liberation (NAIMSAL). Michael Zinzun, who founded the Southern Africa Support Coalition, had been a member of the Black Panther Party. Ron Wilkins, who served as the driving local force in organizing around the cultural boycott, had been a part of the Student Non-Violent Coordinating Committee as well as the Patrice Lumumba Coalition. Thus while communists, revolutionary nationalists, and left nationalists disagreed on multiple issues, including organisational methods, conceptions of class, and the efficacy of crossracial coalitions, the goal of preventing Black American entertainers from allowing their talents to be utilized in support of apartheid allowed common work to take place.

Toward Unity in Action-California and the Cultural Boycott

Activism around the cultural boycott drew in a variety of black radical formations, including the SASC and the NAIMSAL. From 1982 to 1990, however, Unity in Action (UIA) formed the primary Southern California group active around the cultural boycott. Formed as a response to the African National Congress declaration of 1982 as the “Year of Unity in Action,” UIA conducted a prolonged campaign aimed at building support for the cultural boycott in Los Angeles. In the period that followed Soweto and the murder of Steve Biko, calls for the complete isolation of South Africa accelerated, although demands for a policy of academic and cultural exclusion began as early as 1958 (Thorn 2006, 127-131; Fieldhouse 2005, 95-111.) During the next two decades, the world of sport was arguably the most visible arena in which attempts to isolate Pretoria took place. (Nixon 1982; Archer and Bouillon 1982). Alongside this, increasing activity took place among writers, visual artists and, especially, musicians. In 1980, the UN General Assembly adopted resolution 35/206, which called on “writers, artists and musicians,” as well as independent states, to terminate all cultural and academic links with South Africa.

In October of 1983, the UN's Special Committee Against Apartheid began issuing lists of entertainers who violated the boycott by performing in South Africa.

The aggregation of this activity made expressive culture highly visible sector of political activism. Gerald Horne details the depth of cultural activity in New York (Horne 2019, 766). By 1986, British cultural workers had formed Artists Against Apartheid, and cognate groups arose in the United States as well. Benefits featuring musicians—some South African, some not—were commonplace, and the anthemic songs of the external campaign, including “Sun City,” “Biko,” and “Free Nelson Mandela,” had emerged as well. The cultural boycott did have its contradictions. The ANC spoke in favor of continued isolation but sought to promote examples of what it considered democratic and insurgent culture. As Roger Fieldhouse notes, calls to boycott “the apartheid regime but not South Africa” struck many British activists as difficult to carry forward in practice, although this dynamic does not seem to have been as much at issue in the United States, at least among African Americans (Fieldhouse 2005, 107).

The Los Angeles-based formation Unity in Action emerged from the Patrice Lumumba Coalition, a left nationalist organisation with chapters in Los Angeles and New York. Led in Los Angeles by Ron Wilkins, and in New York by longtime nationalist activist Elombe Brath, Unity in Action (UIA) was both explicitly pan-Africanist and anticapitalist, advocating for the Grenadian and Zimbabwean revolutions as well as opposing US interventions in Central America. Although closer in some ways to the basic ideas of the PAC, as was the case with many Black American radicals, political circumstances pushed UIA toward the ANC.³ The UIA operated many of its events from the Black Employees Association office and they described their base as “LA’s Black

³ During the 1970s, sharp splits emerged in the United States around the question of the Soviet Union, China, anticolonial revolution in Africa, and coalitional politics within the United States. For left nationalists, the efficacy of anti-imperialism on the part of the Cubans, MPLA, FRELIMO, and Nicaraguans, as well as the emergence of English-speaking Marxist revolutionaries in Grenada, made the political perspective of the ANC more attractive, despite their misgivings about the viability of nonracialist politics in either the North American or Southern African context. The inability of PAC cadres to establish the same sort of international base proved another critical point.

working class, which includes a cross section of blue collar and professional workers, students, and the unemployed” (Unity in Action 1983; Wilkins 1987).

In the context of an African American population buffeted by severe economic dislocation, it is worth dwelling on the terminology that Wilkins and the UIA chose in respect to class politics. Between 1975 and 1990, tens of thousands of highly paid industrial jobs left Los Angeles, including the shuttering of factories located in heavily black and Mexican American areas (Soja, Morales, and Wolff, 1983). Auto production, once second only to Detroit in scale, disappeared almost entirely. Moreover, in the 13 months between the Rodney King beating and the rebellion that followed the acquittal of the police accused of attacking him, more than 100,000 jobs were lost in predominantly black areas of Los Angeles alone (Coalition to Stop Plant Closures 1975; Labor Community Strategy Center 1992). This led to a “social and economic bifurcation” in which the fortunes of the black poor and the black middle class diverged more sharply than ever before (Grant, Oliver, and James 1996). Thus in contrast to the point of production struggles of the sort described by Peter Cole, the language of the “black working class” indicated a desire to cast the spatially-bound, over-policed, and economically marginalized residents of South Los Angeles as capable of striking the same sort of direct blow generated elsewhere by dockworkers or other industrial laborers (Cole 2013; Kelley 2014; Polaroid 1970).

Unity in Action Members. Wilkins is pictured in the back row, second from left. (Image courtesy of Ron Wilkins)

Wilkins recognized that the cultural boycott took place amidst a profound transformation in the public portrayal of African Americans in the American mass media. The late 1970s and early 1980s marked the first major turn toward corporate marketing of “diversity.” This was a moment of crossover appeal of black athletes and celebrities, from the vacuous racelessness of O.J. Simpson to the carefully calibrated suburbanism of Bill Cosby. From Magic Johnson and Michael Jordan to Michael Jackson and Gary Coleman, black faces achieved new prominence in American life. This marked a major turnaround from earlier periods, when figures like Paul Robeson, Joe Louis, or Duke Ellington, could not, whatever their relative popularity with whites, ever truly stand as “symbols” of America. Wilkins noted the implications for this moment, writing, “we are all aware of how greatly images and trends depicted on television influence public opinion. This is

especially true for Black people, in media because, for better or worse, the media has turned our leaders into celebrities and our celebrities into leaders” (Unity in Action, 1983).

Although it made specific reference to developments in the United States, Wilkins’s comment about the inversion of celebrity and leadership bore directly upon the movement against apartheid. Tomaselli and Shepperson (2009) describe the 1987 television series *Mandela* as a “superhero tale” in which Glover’s “towering” physicality marginalizes Walter Sisulu and Oliver Tambo, thereby reducing the liberation struggle to the agency of a single man. Moreover, in 1987 few Americans knew what the imprisoned Mandela looked like, which augmented, as William Sudderth observed, the tendency to conflate Mandela and Glover (Tomaselli and Shepperson 2009, 33). As a film produced principally with the aim of humanizing Mandela before British and American audiences steeped in the logics of Reagan and Thatcher’s Cold War(fare), *Mandela* replaced visions of a socialist South Africa with what Lothiko Modisane (2014, 232) describes as a narrative of Christian deliverance and renewal. To this, one can say “it could be worse.” Although Glover bore scant resemblance to Mandela, and while the 1987 miniseries misrepresented basic elements of the liberation struggle, at least Glover was an activist voice whose commitment to pan-Africanism and socialism was a matter of record. On separate occasions, Hollywood executives had considered casting comedians Richard Pryor and Eddie Murphy as Malcolm X, a decision trumped by onetime plans to present white actress Julia Roberts as abolitionist Harriet Tubman.

In this context, the cultural boycott challenged both apartheid and a politics that cast American racial progress as a matter of celebrity representation. Public mobilizations that aimed to “name and shame” black celebrities constituted a popular reaction to a growing class gap amongst African Americans by reminding those who were moving ahead that they were ultimately beholden to a broader community. Unity In Action compelled artists and entertainers to not only honor the boycott but also to become active members of the struggle or risk losing prestige, authenticity, and ultimately, wealth. “It should be fairly evident by now to even the casual observer,” one flyer noted, “that boycotts and

demonstrations have been the key to at least getting the offending artists attention.” Beyond this, Wilkins continued, “any genuine effort to stop artists from going to South Africa must contain some punitive measure to make the exorbitant sums being offered less attractive” (Wilkins 1984).⁴

This cultural activism stood in stark contrast to the vision of African/African American relations pursued by Los Angeles Mayor Tom Bradley. First elected to office in 1973, Tom Bradley was a former policeman who managed to assemble a victorious coalition in a city where black voters comprised no more than a fifth of the total electorate. As a black mayor governing a large city at the head of an interracial coalition, Bradley was a popular and influential figure across the political spectrum. Staff members connected to his administration began journeying to Africa soon after he took office, and by 1978, Bradley had established a Task Force for Africa/Los Angeles Relations. In 1981, the task force organised the “Treasures of Ancient Nigeria: Legacy of 2000 Years” exhibit, which displayed precolonial artifacts from the Ivory Coast, Kenya, Nigeria, and Zaire (Ianco-Starrels 1981). The task force invested hundreds of thousands of public dollars into programs aimed at trade relationships and African American investment into African nations—many of them brutal dictatorships like Zaire and Nigeria. Between 1979 and 1984, under a mayoral push to expand trade with Africa, Bradley and his aides built new reciprocal trade links with at least fifteen African states. (Bradley Administrative Papers Box 5065).

Commerce, rather than politics, was Bradley’s goal. As such, the task force was never intended to play a role in the divestment campaign or other anti-apartheid activities. Although he would eventually champion a municipal divestment law, Bradley took very few steps, before 1985, to oppose South Africa. In 1980, in response to a letter challenging him to oppose the opening of the consulate in Los Angeles, he argued against “severing links,” instead calling for “communication” and “constructive interest.” This Reaganesque language allowed Bradley to voice quiet disapproval for South Africa without placing his political capital on the line or jeopardising financial links that might

⁴ Wilkins, “Towards a Program to End Cultural Collaboration,” 2.

prove necessary should he realise his ultimately unsuccessful ambition of becoming governor of California. In 1982, during his first gubernatorial run, he attended the grand opening of the South African Consulate in Beverly Hills. Bradley subsequently awarded a key to the city to South African Consul General (and former military intelligence officer and occasional Savimbi spokesperson) Sean Cleary. Bradley eventually expressed ambivalence about the event, although photographs of the smiling mayor, TransAfrica head Randall Robinson noted, became a propaganda tool “included in every South African publication sent around the world” (Unity in Action, 1985).

At the time of Bradley’s meeting with Cleary, the South African government was recasting itself as a society undergoing reform. Alongside internal changes like the adoption of the Tricameral Parliament, Pretoria continued to solicit the entry of international figures. With the establishment of the Beverly Hills consulate, antiapartheid activists believed that Pretoria had begun to lobby for the reentry into the Olympics, soon to be held in Los Angeles. The black mayor of America’s second largest city had become a pawn. “It is ironic that while fascist South Africa has been barred from the Olympics since 1970,” UIA (1983) argued, “Tom Bradley has seen fit to graciously welcome its consulate to LA—the site of the 1984 Olympic Games.”

In 1983, UIA joined organisations vocally opposed to South Africa’s reentry efforts. The Ad Hoc Committee to Keep South Africa Out of the Olympics included Elliot Barker of UIA, Maxine Waters, Randall Robinson, Dennis Brutus, and Michigan State University Athletic Director Frank Beeman. African Activist Association and UCLA graduate student Robin Kelley chaired the Ad Hoc Committee, which lobbied the Los Angeles Olympic Organising Committee (LAOOC) and organised direct actions. After South Africa officially ended their bid for reentry into the 1984 games, Ad Hoc Committee members joined ten thousand protesters in the Survivalfest 84 march through downtown Los Angeles. The following week, the committee organised a spirited consular protest as well (Ad Hoc Committee 1983; Kelley 2014, 241).

In December 1984, Unity in Action publicly opposed the NAACP's Image Awards as well as the Spingarn Medal ceremony the following month. A contemporary of the ANC—the two organisations having been founded in 1909 and 1912, respectively—America's oldest extant civil rights organisation had long contested cultural representations deemed offensive while rewarding those who contributed to the promotion of positive images. Since 1915, the NAACP has awarded the Spingarn Medal in honor of outstanding achievement by an African American, while in 1967, the organization added Image Awards first for cultural workers. In 1984, Tina Turner and Danniebelle Hall had been nominated for Image Awards and Bob Hope had been named an Honorary Chairperson of the December proceedings. All three of the performers were on the UN list of entertainers who had performed in South Africa. In 1983, Bradley was an honorary committee member and the recipient of the Spingarn Medal.

Under pressure from Unity in Action, the Beverly Hills/Hollywood NAACP rescinded the nominations of Hall and Turner as well as Hope's honorary chairpersonship. In likely response to the pressure, the Nobel Peace Prize Recipient Bishop Desmond Tutu was honored with the Stevie Wonder Key of Life award at the Image Awards. Wilkins and the UIA had appealed directly to Bishop Tutu for his support. Out of respect for Bishop Tutu, UIA scuttled its planned demonstration of the December ceremony. Despite misgivings from many antiapartheid activists, including California Assemblywoman Maxine Waters, UIA publicly confronted Bradley at the Spingarn Medal ceremony (Unity in Action 1985). Although unsuccessful in scuttling Bradley's award, the pressure pushed Bradley toward a more aggressive position against apartheid, and his staff developed a plan to pull Los Angeles pension funds out of companies tied to South Africa as well as banks who traded in Krugerrands.

Unity in Action also launched an offensive against the film industry. Following a *Daily Variety* article that noted that the Cannon Group had either shot or distributed twenty films in South Africa, UIA pressure led Cannon, a major film production studio with extensive holdings in Europe as well as the US, to abandon further involvement in South Africa (Wilkins 1988). In addition to entertainers, UIA targeted production companies

and financial backers of films produced or distributed in South Africa. As with their protests against the 10-part South African-produced miniseries *Shaka Zulu* (1986), the position taken by UIA and their allies, such as the Coalition Against Black Exploitation (CABE), conflicted with the general perception of a Black American viewing public hungry for anything considered positive black content. Their positions did, however, align with the African National Congress and revolutionary forces in South Africa more generally. Unity in Action took direction from the ANC positions and several of their flyers featured the insignia of the ANC's armed wing, Umkhonto we Sizwe (Spear of the Nation). On 11 October 1985, UIA organised a public forum on the liberation struggles in South Africa, Angola, and Namibia at the Black Employees Association in the Crenshaw District. Organised as a part of the International Day of Solidarity with South African Political Prisoners, UIA aired the film *Generations of Resistance* (1979) by the radical documentarian Peter Davis (Wilkins 1988).

Produced with the financial backing of Pretoria, the ANC opposed *Shaka Zulu* in South Africa and UIA protested its broadcast in Southern California. Wilkins noted that the series received 2.5 million dollars from the government-run South African Broadcasting Corporation (SABC). Featuring a fictional plotline in which a white doctor saves Shaka's life, *Shaka Zulu* offered a paternalistic account in which armed whites were necessary to prevent a descent into chaos. Los Angeles Times columnist Howard Rosenberg (1986) called the production "gory, foolish, and demeaning" Wilkins agreed, suggesting the series argued, "if it were not for white intrusion, the land would have stayed in savagery" (Valle 1986, H8). UIA launched a series of protests against local TV station KCOP, which broadcast the program. Apparently ignorant of the fact Shaka was a contemporary of Thomas Jefferson, rather than Jesus Christ, KCOP station manager Rick Feldman stated: "It showed blacks as they were 2,000 years ago. This has nothing to do with South Africa today." By blockading the station entrance with banners rebuking "KKKOP," Unity in Action argued that *everything* about the production had to do with contemporary South Africa—and with the United States as well.

Presenting a radical counterculture to Southern California's cultural industry, Unity in Action weaponised humour and imagination in their protests. In addition to adding names to the list, UIA hounded "cultural mercenaries" who visited South Africa throughout Southern California. In a September 1985 protest of Shirley Bassey, the UIA wrapped their flyer with a banner that read "Sold Out to Apartheid" (Unity in Action 1987a). In 1986 and 1987, protestors greeted Ray Charles with picket signs that read, "Hit the road, Ray, and don't cha come back no more!" in a mocking reference to Charles' most famous song (Unity in Action, 1987b). (Fig. 3) The UIA also published home addresses of stars and distributed them to the public. In doing so, UIA activists subverted the star culture of Southern California, shattering the secured world of anonymity in which the personal beliefs and practices of Hollywood talent was rarely scrutinized. By publishing the addresses of entertainers who violated the cultural boycott, the UIA transformed celebrity home tours—available via publicly sold "star maps"—into a public gaffe. Combining public confrontations with home blockades, UIA sought to ensure that entertainers who broke the boycott would have no safe place to retreat.

Unity in Action members picket Ray Charles. Photo courtesy of Ron Wilkins

In obtaining and distributing home addresses UIA advanced a strategy subsequently adopted by labour organisers and immigrant rights activists in Southern California such as Justice for Janitors and the Korean Immigrants Workers Alliance (Cleeland 2000; Milkman 2006, 7, 17-21). In a December 1985 correspondence with Amer Araim from the Centre Against Apartheid in New York, Wilkins shared the home addresses of Linda Ronstadt, Frank Sinatra, Danniebelle Hall, and Ray Charles. When Unity in Action was unable to directly contact performers, they obtained their information unofficially through allies inside industry unions and guilds. As Wilkins noted at the time, “LA’s distinction as a primary entertainment, film, and record producing center makes it ideal for cultural boycott activity” (Unity in Action, 1983).

Wilkins acknowledged the political possibilities opened by the emergence of new forms of celebrity that portrayed Black Americans as affluent, fashionable, and palatable to white audiences. Although the apotheosis of this process, the *Cosby Show*, was set in Brooklyn, Los Angeles was its center. Here, Magic Johnson and Kareem Abdul-Jabbar headlined the “showtime” Los Angeles Lakers, who dominated professional basketball and whose televised games featured constant courtside shots of Hollywood celebrities. Michael Jackson’s Encino residence, where he recorded *Thriller* and developed the moonwalk, was located just over the Sepulveda pass from Hollywood and Beverly Hills. OJ Simpson, arguably the first Black American to achieve widespread commercial popularity among whites, called the city home as well. Alongside all of this glamour stood the administration of Tom Bradley, a black figurehead for a multiracial city that had, until this moment, viewed its black residents most through the lens of an infamous riot. Indeed, in the decade before Magic, Michael Jackson, and OJ, the most visible symbolic figure associated with Black Los Angeles had been the fictional Fred Sanford, a caustic, ghetto-dwelling owner of a junk business run out of his home in Watts.

The presence of independent media in Los Angeles aided the cultural boycott. Both the black-owned radio station KJLH and the *Sentinel*, Los Angeles’ oldest Black newspaper, offered favorable coverage of the campaign. Wilkins also produced the bi-weekly radio show “Continent to Continent” on the progressive independent station KPFK, whose signal covered a metropolitan area of millions of listeners.⁵ Wilkins’s guests included Sotirios Moursoris, Director of the United Nations Centre Against Apartheid; SWAPO central committee member Mose Tjitendero; Musekiwa Kumbula, a Zimbabwean active with Z.A.N.U.; and Serge Mukendi, U. S. Representative of the Congolese National Liberation Front. As a result, listeners heard weekly updates not only about South Africa, but about the frontline states as well (Unity in Action 1987; Mukendi 1983).

⁵ Because KPFK broadcasts under an old license into which its signal strength is grandfathered, it is able to transmit at a much higher power than its listenership would normally allow. In 1990, the entire service area of the station reached between one third and half of all Californians. The station’s approach to South Africa was inconsistent. In 1987, amidst the controversy that attended Paul Simon’s *Graceland* recording and tour, Ladysmith Black Mambazo made their US debut on the station.

The cultural boycott illustrates the particularity of anti-apartheid activity in Southern California, where activities targeted the region's primary area of international influence. Although a small organization, Unity in Action had an outsized impact, altering the behavior people whose reach was truly global. Of the more than one hundred celebrities directly confronted, only black poet Nikki Giovanni, musician Ray Charles, and Mexican American singer Linda Rondstadt refused to sign pledges forswearing further cooperation with the regime. The Los Angeles chapter of Unity in Action received pledges of support from dozens of celebrities, including the Temptations, Barry Manilow, Tina Turner, Pia Zadora, Terry Gibbs, Tom Jones, while facilitating the active cooperation of local figures like visual artist John Outterbridge, Inner City Cultural Center founder C. Bernard Jackson, and actress Frances Williams.

One can question what effect Unity in Action, or the broader anti-apartheid movement in Los Angeles had. This risks asking the wrong question. As Robin Kelley reminds us, "too often our measurements for evaluating social movements pivot around whether or not they 'succeeded' in realizing their visions, rather than on the merits" of the goals they champion (Kelley 2002, IX). Mass activity sometimes leads to direct breakthroughs, whether reformist or revolutionary. More often, however, movements achieve something more ephemeral and harder to categorize. They shift the sense of what is legible, desirable, or possible. They inject politics into spheres of life, such as mainstream entertainment, where it is usually absent. They point out connections that had previously escaped our attention, in ways that draw in new people, thus ensuring that defeats are never final.

With this in mind, we should avoid drawing too many specific conclusions about the ultimate importance of Los Angeles-based antiapartheid activity in the wider struggle for a democratic South Africa. At the same time, there are lessons to be learned, and observations that can be made.

In Los Angeles, activism around the cultural boycott achieved effects well beyond that initially envisioned by the relatively small number of organisers directly concerned with

the campaign. Described by the U.N. Centre Against Apartheid (1985) as being “in the forefront of the struggle against Apartheid,” Unity in Action proved highly adept at forcing artists who had travelled to South Africa to refuse to do so again, and could realistically claim to be the most successful North American group active around these questions. As a consequence, the group was commended by U.N. staffer Pam Maponga (1985), who lauded their “enormous efforts” in supporting the cultural boycott. The success of Unity in Action came as a direct consequence of the recognition of the possibility of building a campaign upon two highly strategic terrains—the liminal place of Black American entertainers as emerging crossover stars still beholden to a racially defined minority community, and the desire of white entertainers to avoid the stain of collaboration with racism—in ways that linked race, class, and internationalism.

Pressure upon cultural producers generated a functional unity among Black American radicals, who maintained a working-class base as a consequence of their presence during earlier moments of political activity. The visibility of confrontations with black celebrities drew attention to the divergent fortunes of African Americans across the class spectrum, which in turn augmented efforts to describe the struggle against apartheid as part of domestic struggle against white supremacy inside the United States in a city governed by a Black mayor and represented via the lens of Black celebrity. In other cities, the docks, or the factory floor, or campus lecture halls, or boardrooms, provided similar opportunities. But in Los Angeles, at the heart of the spectacle, the movement took advantage what former Los Angeles resident Bernard Magubane described in another context as “a unique interpenetration of objective and subjective factors. (Magubane 2010).” Put another way, it engaged the border between real life and reel life.

coda

The 1989 blockbuster film *Lethal Weapon 2* stands out amongst the mainstream cinema of which it at first seems a part. Featuring longtime activist Danny Glover, who two years earlier had played the title role in the *Mandela* television drama, *Lethal Weapon 2*

incorporated elements common to interracial “buddy” action films of the 1980s.⁶ In contrast to the militarized hyperpatriotism of *Rambo*, *Commando*, or *Red Dawn*, *Lethal Weapon 2* engaged multiple topics at the heart of local antiapartheid activity, including the foregrounding of state violence, the assertion of a global alliance of white supremacists, and the insistence on the self-activity of ordinary people. *Lethal Weapon 2* set the interracial duo of Roger Murtaugh, a senior police detective, and the younger Vietnam veteran Martin Riggs against a cabal of murderous drug dealing and money laundering South African consular officials headed by the fictional Minister of Diplomatic Affairs, Arjun Rudd. Even without planned scenes—including an airplane full of cocaine that explodes over Los Angeles in a grim echo of contemporaneous assertions of CIA complicity in fostering the crack cocaine epidemic—the film touched upon the neoliberal restructuring of the Southern California economy, the contradictions of Black representation, the links between campus and community protest, and the possibility of black internationalism.

In an iconic scene, Murtaugh and their special asset Leo Getz distract an official at the Beverly Hills consulate while Riggs sneaks upstairs to confront Rudd. Chanting protesters march in the background. Although national audiences may well have associated the pickets with the news coverage of celebrity-led Free South Africa Movement protests that targeted the Pretoria’s embassy in Washington, episodic attempts to impede consular operations in Los Angeles had begun years before. By the time of the film’s release, moreover, junior high and high school students had made repeated attempts to invade and occupy the building (Jones 1989).⁷ In the film, protestors hold ANC flags and antiapartheid signs as Murtaugh (Danny Glover) requests a visa to travel to South Africa. When asked by an incredulous white consular official why a Black man would want to travel to South Africa, Murtaugh replies: “To join up with my oppressed

⁶ Glover was perhaps the most politically committed actor of his generation, having been part of the Third World Liberation Front during the pivotal 1968 strike, during which time he was jailed for several months. Later, he participated in campaigns in support of multiple labor unions and progressive forces in Haiti, Brazil, Ecuador, Nigeria, and Sudan. Apartheid, however, remained a specific focus of his activism during the 1980s.

⁷ Author Widener was a participant in these demonstrations as a part of the Los Angeles Student Coalition.

brothers. To take up the struggle against the tyranny of the racist, fascist, white minority regime. One man! One vote! Free South Africa, you dumb son of a bitch!”

Thirty years have passed since the film’s release, and since Mandela’s visit to Los Angeles. In this time, both South Africa and the United States have had black presidents, and both have seen growing inequality. Both have seen mass black mobilisations, anti-capitalist in orientation and conscious of the limitations of previous forms and moments of struggle. Yet neither the growth of the Movement for Black Lives and the Economic Freedom Fighters nor the more episodic interventions of North American sports protests or South Africa’s Rhodes Must Fall protests have as yet proved able to effectively connect across national spaces or produce a mass movement capable of reshaping either society. Indeed, amidst a rising tide of right-wing populism around the globe, and against the backdrop of perhaps the weakest period of connection between black North Americans and the Africans on the continent in more than a century, it is worth returning our attention to an earlier moment, when organizers on both sides of the Atlantic took up the fight against what the Southern Africa Support Committee (1977) called “a common enemy of the peoples” of both Southern Africa and the United States.

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